

DESCRIPTION OF THE LEVEL OF PATIENT SATISFACTION WITH NURSING SERVICES in patient DR. DRAJAT PRAWIRANEGARA SERANG

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ABSTRACT: Prime nursing services are services provided to patients based on quality standard to meet the needs and wants of patients so that patients can get satisfaction (Qingwei, 2012) The purpose of this research is to know the description of Patient Satisfaction Level on Nursing Service in Inpatient Room of RSUD dr. Drajat Prawiranegara Serang 2018. Variables in this study are attitude, action, attention, responsibility, ability, appearance. The research method used is descriptive with the number of samples 92. Sampling technique used is a quota sampling technique. The results of each variable were satisfied with attitude result (80,4%), action (57,6%), attention (48,9%), responsibility (79,3%), ability (75,0%), and appearance (65.2%). Suggestion from researcher expected RSUD dr. Drajat Prawiranegara can improve the reliability and quality of nursing services in order to achieve excellent service for patients.

Keywords: Description of patient's satisfaction level, excellent nursing service.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, changes in the health sector are currently happening so rapidly, free competition in all health systems, especially hospitals. In achieving a healthy Indonesia, all services in the health sector, especially hospitals, must be able to compete with other hospitals. Hospitals as health service providers must provide high quality and professional services to every consumer (patient) who uses the services at the hospital, so that consumers are satisfied with the services provided at the hospital (Linda Ntombizodwa et al., 2020; Rahayu, 2018)

In its development, in order for the hospital to survive, the hospital must be able to provide satisfaction in providing services to patients. Because customer demands from time to time will increase and it is not uncommon for complaints, hopes, reports that they submit as part of an effort to defend their rights as recipients of health services

Nursing services in hospitals are an inseparable part of health services as a whole, even as a determining factor for the quality of services and the image of the hospital in the eyes of the community. Based on that, organizational, administrative and technical nursing services cannot be separated from hospital services in general. Nursing services require accuracy because it has a mission to manage the largest number of human resources in the hospital (Ernawati & Lusiani, 2019; Rowley, 2000) Nurses as health workers with most patients are required to provide the best service in the form of caring behavior where caring is an act of caring that aims to provide physical care and pay attention to emotions while increasing the sense of security and safety to patients. Caring behavior given by nurses to patients can increase patient satisfaction (Susilawati et al., 2018)

Satisfaction can arise from the quality of service in accordance with the code of ethics and professional service standards. Nursing services are an integral part of the standard of service for health professionals

in hospitals. Nurses have a fairly dominant role in providing satisfaction to patients because nurses are near the patient for 24 hours, it is also mentioned that 70% of health workers in the hospital is a nurse. Nurses also provide comprehensive health services including bio, psycho, socio, cultural and spiritual services. Patients' perceptions are also the most important thing in patient satisfaction, so the performance of nurses is often a measure of the merits of services in inpatient installations (Linda Ntombizodwa et al., 2020; Pepito & Locsin, 2019)

One of the nursing services at the hospital is excellent service, where excellent service is professional service, fast, clean, friendly and of course services that provide satisfaction to patients. To get to prime service, adequate facilities and infrastructure are needed, besides that, it also requires human resources who meet the requirements, both quality and quantity. Officers who have high knowledge, reliable skills and good behavior (Frood et al., 2018; Linda Ntombizodwa et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2017)

Based on a preliminary study conducted by researchers in April 2019 in the inpatient room, from the results of interviews with 10 patients, 7 patients said they were not satisfied and 3 patients said they were satisfied. The patient's dissatisfaction was caused by the nurse's unfriendly attitude and some of the procedures given were not as expected. Based on the description above, the formulation of the problem of the research that will be carried out is "Description of Patient Satisfaction Levels of Nursing Services in the Inpatient Room of dr. Drajat Prawiranegara Serang 2019.

Understanding Patient Satisfaction

The patient is a bio-psycho-socio-economic-cultural-spiritual being, meaning that he needs to fulfill his needs, desires and hopes from the biological (health), psychological (satisfaction), socio-economic (shelter, clothing, food and social affiliation) aspects.), and cultural aspects (Winasih et al., 2015).

Satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment in a person that arises after comparing their perceptions or impressions of the performance or results of a product or service and their expectations. Thus the level of satisfaction is the appearance that is felt is proportional to expectations, the customer will feel satisfied (Winasih et al., 2015) Satisfaction is a model of the gap between expectations (performance standards that should be) and the actual performance received by the customer (Susilawati et al., 2018; Winasih et al., 2015).

Patient satisfaction is a level of patient feelings that arise as a result of the performance of health services obtained after the patient compares with what he expected (Luthviatin et al., 2011; Martins & Proença, 2014; Pambreni et al., 2019). Patient satisfaction is a level of patient feeling that arises as a result of the health service performance he gets after the patient compares with what he expected. New patients will feel satisfied if the health service performance they get is the same or exceeds what they expected and vice versa. Customer (patient) satisfaction occurs when what the needs, wants, and expectations of the customer (patient) can be fulfilled, then the customer (patient) will feel satisfied (Winasih et al., 2015).

Factors affecting satisfaction

Factors that affect patient satisfaction according to (Winasih et al., 2015) are as follows:

1. The quality of the product or service.

Patients will feel satisfied when their evaluation results show that the quality of the product or service used.

2. Price.

Price is an important aspect in determining quality in order to achieve patient satisfaction. The more expensive the treatment, the patient has greater expectations.

3. Emotional.

Patients who feel proud and believe that others admire consumers when in this case the patient chooses a health care institution that already has views, tends to have a higher level of satisfaction.

4. Performance.

For example, the form of this performance; speed, convenience, comfort for nurses in providing medical services, especially during relatively fast healing times, ease in meeting patient needs and comfort provided, namely paying attention to cleanliness, hospitality and completeness of hospital equipment

5. Aesthetics.

Aesthetics is a hospital attraction that can be captured by the five senses. For example: nurse hospitality, complete equipment and so on.

6. Product characteristics.

This product is a physical property, including buildings and decorations. Product characteristics include the appearance of the building, cleanliness and the types of room classes provided and their accessories.

7. Service.

Friendly service for hospital staff, speed in service. Health service institutions are considered good if they prioritize patient needs in providing services. Satisfaction arises from the patient's first impression of the nursing services provided. For example: fast service, responsiveness and friendliness in providing nursing services.

8. Location.

Location, including the location of the room and its environment. Is one aspect that determines the consideration in choosing a health service institution. Generally, the closer the location is to an urban center or one that is easily accessible, the easier it is to transport and a good environment, the more choices it will become for patients.

9. Facilities.

Completeness of facilities also determines the assessment of patient satisfaction, for example, health facilities, including facilities and infrastructure, parking lots, waiting rooms and comfortable inpatient rooms. Although this is not vital in determining the assessment of patient satisfaction, health care institutions need to pay attention to facilities in formulating strategies to attract consumers.

10. Communication.

Communication is the procedure for information provided by service providers and complaints from patients. How are the complaints from patients quickly accepted by service providers, especially nurses in providing assistance to patient complaints.

11. Atmosphere.

The atmosphere includes security and familiarity. A calm, comfortable, cool and beautiful atmosphere will greatly affect patient satisfaction in the healing process. In addition, it is not only for patients who enjoy it, but other people who visit will be very happy and give positive opinions so that it will impress visitors to the health service institution.

12. Visual design.

Visual design includes uncomplicated room decor, buildings and street designs. Layout and decoration also determine a comfort.

Definition of Excellent Service

Prime nursing service is the service provided to patients based on quality standards to meet the needs and desires of patients so that patients can get satisfaction (Ang, 2019; Rahayu, 2018). Excellent service is basically shown to provide satisfaction to patients. The services provided by the hospital must be of high quality and have five main quality dimensions, namely: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy. Whether they are aware of or not, the appearance (tangibles) of the hospital is the main point that customers or patients pay attention to. The issues of reliability, responsiveness and assurance are sensitive issues and often lead to conflicts. In this process the factor of concern (empathy) for the patient cannot be neglected by the hospital (Frood et al., 2018; van der Heever & van der Merwe, 2019).

II. METHOD

Research design

This type of research used in this research is descriptive research,

Location and Time of Research Research Sites

In the inpatient room of dr. Drajat Prawiranegara Serang.

Research time

The time of the research was carried out during July 2019.

Population and Population Sample

The population of this study were all patients in the inpatient room (Mina, Arafah, Muzdalifah, Melati 1, Melati 2, Anggrek 1, Anggrek 2, Dahlia and Cempaka in dr. Drajat Prawiranegara Hospital in 2019 in the last 4 months.

Sample

The sample used in this study is a quota sampling technique, where the sampling is based on certain considerations and is made by the researcher himself.

Data Collection Techniques

The technique used by researchers in collecting this data is to use a questionnaire with reference to the theoretical basis. The questions to be asked are 30 questions developed based on excellent service, where the questionnaire for each variable has 5 questions out of 5 of these 5 questions, 4 of which are positive questions and 1 question is negative.

Research Instrument

The instrument in this study was a questionnaire developed based on excellent service which included: Attitude, Action, Attention, Accountability, Ability, Appearance (Irawan, Nasiatin et al., 2020; Sulistiyani et al., 2014)

Data processing

Data processing is done manually first, then statistically using a computer program and through several stages, namely: checking data (editing), coding (coding) data entry (entry) checking data (cleaning)

Data analysis

The purpose of data analysis is to simplify data in a form that is easier to read and interpretasi.

Uji Normalitas Data

In this study, the mean value of attitude variable was 4.22. The denominational test of data from the comparison of Skewness and the standard error of the action variable was obtained: $-0.345 / 0.251 = 1.374$. Obtained the mean value of the action variable is 3.59. The denominational test of the data from the comparison of Skewness and standard error of the attention variable was obtained: $-0.179 / 0.251 =$

0.713. Obtained the mean value of attention variable is 3.33. The denominational test of the data from the comparison of Skewness and the standard error of the accountability variable was obtained: $- 0.670 / 0.251 = 2.669$.

From the accountability variable, the median value was 4.00. The denominational test of the data from the Skewness comparison and the standard error of the ability variable is obtained: $- 0.290 / 0.253 = 1.146$. Obtained the mean value 3.91. The denominational test of the data from the comparison of Skewness and standard error of the appearance variable was obtained: $-0.273 / 0.251 = 1.087$. Obtained a mean value of 3.91.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Distribution of patient satisfaction levels based on the attention of nurses in the inpatient room of the RSUD dr. Drajat Prawiranegara Serang in 2018

Patient satisfaction based on (<i>attention</i>) Nurse	Quantity	Presentase	Patient satisfaction based on (<i>ability</i>) Nurse	Quantity	Presentase
Not Satisfaction	47	51,1%	Not Satisfaction	23	25,0%
Satisfaction	45	48,9%	Satisfaction	69	75,0%
Total	92	100,0%	Total	92	100,0%

Based on table 5.3, the results obtained from 92 respondents, as many as 45 patients (48.9%) said they were satisfied, while 47 patients (51.1%) said they were not satisfied with the nurse's attention to excellent nursing services.

Table 2. Distribution of patient satisfaction levels based on the responsibilities of nurses in the inpatient room of dr. Drajat Prawiranegara Serang Hospital in 2019.

Patient satisfaction based on (<i>responsibility</i>) Nurse	Quantity	Presentase
Not Satisfaction	19	20,7%
Satisfaction	73	79,3%
Total	92	100,0%

Based on table 5.4, the results obtained from 92 respondents mostly said they were satisfied, as many as 73 patients (79.3%) said they were satisfied with the sense of responsibility of nurses based on excellent nursing services.

Based on table 5.5, the results obtained from 92 respondents, most of the respondents said they were satisfied, namely as many as 69 patients (75.0%) said they were satisfied with the ability of nurses to have excellent nursing service.

Table 3. Distribution of patient satisfaction levels based on the appearance of nurses in the inpatient room of dr. Drajat Prawiranegara Serang Hospital in 2019.

Patient satisfaction based on (<i>appearance</i>) Nurse	Quantity	Presentase
Not Satisfaction	32	34,8%
Satisfaction	60	65,2%
Total	92	100,0%

Based on table 5.6, the results of 92 respondents showed that almost the majority of respondents were satisfied, namely as many as 60 patients (65.2%) said they were satisfied with the appearance of nurses on excellent nursing services

IV. CONCLUSION

The description of the patient's decision level based on the nurse's attitude showed that most of the patients said they were satisfied with the nurse's attitude, namely 74 (80.4%) patients who said they were satisfied. The description of the level of patient satisfaction based on the action (action) showed that 53 (57.6%) patients said they were satisfied with the actions given by the nurse. The description of the level of patient satisfaction based on attention showed that 45 (48.9%) patients said they were satisfied with the attention given by nurses. However, the number of respondents who expressed dissatisfaction was more than those who expressed satisfaction, namely 47 (51.1%) patients. The description of the level of patient satisfaction based on the responsibility (accountability) shows that most respondents expressed satisfaction, as many as 73 (79.3%) patients said they were satisfied with the nurse's sense of responsibility. The description of the level of patient satisfaction based on the ability (ability) obtained results as many as 69 (75.0%) patients stated that they were satisfied with the ability of the nurse. The description of the level of patient satisfaction based on appearance showed that 60 (65.2%) patients expressed satisfaction with the appearance of the nurse.

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